

TECHNICAL EDUCATION IN THE COVID 19 ERA: THE CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Education, technical education, Covid 19, pandemic.

ABSTRACT

As the world battles to overcome the challenges caused by the Corona virus pandemic, one possible way Nigeria as a nation can find solutions is through the promotion of technical and innovative education. The study examined the challenges and prospects of technical education amidst the Covid 19 pandemic. The study raised two research questions and objectives and used both primary data generated from research questionnaire items and secondary data from journals and textbooks. The study adopted the survey research design and the simple random sampling technique and administered 300 copies of questionnaires to respondents in the Ken Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic out of which, 258 copies of the questionnaires were retrieved and used for the analysis. The data were presented in a tabular format and analysed with the use of the four point Likert scale. The study adopted human capital theory as its framework of analysis and its findings, amongst others, proves that technical education in Nigeria face challenges arising from; inadequate budgetary provisions, inappropriate curriculum for technical education colleges and institutions and lack of research grants, loans and student sponsorship does not affect technical education in Nigeria. The study amongst others recommends that the government should as a matter of urgency revisit the educational curricula of technical colleges and polytechnics, and that there should be increased budgetary allocations to our education sector especially technical institutions. It is our belief that when the recommendations are adopted and applied by the government, it will go a long way in transforming our technical colleges.

1. Introduction

Towards the closing hours of 2019, the world was hit with the news of the outbreak of a novel disease in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China.

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Cite this article as:

Alafuro E. & Victor I. A. (2022). Technical Education in the Covid 19 Era: the Challenges and Opportunities. *Journal of Advanced Research in Social Sciences*, 5(1): 57-72. <https://doi.org/10.22421/jarss/>

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According to reports, the disease, Corona virus, transmitted from wild animals to man, broke out in Hunan seafood market, a popular market in Wuhan where bats, dogs, snakes and other reptiles cum animals are sold (Johnson, 2021; Orji & Bupo, 2021). Initially, the Chinese government declared it an epidemic and asserted its preparedness to curb its spread; however, between late February and early March, 2020, Europe and America has been practically brought to its knees by the disease. At this point, the World Health Organization (WHO), declared it a pandemic and simultaneously code named it, COVID 19 or novel Corona virus (nCov).

At present the disease has been noticed in almost every part of the globe- despite initial denials by some governments. Available records from daily updates on Cable Network News (CNN) shows that about one hundred and ninety nine (199) million persons have been infected by the disease with more than four million fatalities recorded as at July, 2021 (<https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>). Nigeria recorded her first case of Corona virus on 27th February, 2020 in an Italian who was on a business trip to Lagos; while the second case was reported on February 29, 2020 at Ewekoro, Ogun State via a man who had contact with the Italian index case. Rivers State had her first index case on March 26, 2020 via a young female model who claimed she returned from a trip to some European Countries (Wachukwu et al., 2021 & Johnson, 2021).

Faced with the reality of the pandemic, governments the world over announced various policy measures to stem its tide and protect their citizens from premature extinction. In addition to the WHO recommended washing of hands with soap and water for at least 20 seconds; use of alcohol based hand sanitizers; use of face masks in public places; physical/ social distancing; and where possible, stay at home directives; both the Federal and some State governments (Rivers state inclusive) imposed lockdown on cities for a specific period of time. All of these measures, especially the last one, came with their consequences. It led to closure of academic institutions, places of worship, restaurants, and other businesses with concomitant loss of jobs, hunger, starvation, poverty and acute shortage of many essential household items – with the downtrodden forced to depend wholly on handouts from government and public spirited persons.

Indeed, Covid 19 exposed the vulnerability of man. With Covid 19 it became clear that mankind's strongest power cannot confront nature's minutest challenge. In Nigeria, Covid 19 exposed the short comings in our education system- a system that did not equip its members with vocational skills to cope with trying times like this.

Generally, education is seen as a tool that helps in the advancement of every nation or society at large and to a great extent has the capacity to transform the entire world. It also helps in the equipping members of the society to become useful assets who can serve in different positions in the society. This is rightly explained by Denga (2011) who stated that education will be pointless if it is not aimed at solving societal problems, preserving cultural legacy, creating and discovering new ideas and technologies that are necessary for societal betterment. This emphasizes the need of technical education at a time when the world is in dire need for solutions to the daunting challenges bedeviling mankind.

Technical education revolves around science, technology, engineering and mathematics all of which Onyeche (2019) believes increases imagination, creativity, adaptability, flexibility, and the willingness to learn how to become independent. Thus, when technical education is made compulsory in schools, it will not just help students become innovative and creative, it will help reduce the unemployment rate in the country. More so, Section 7(40) of the National Policy on Education (2004) states *inter alia*, that technical education refers to those aspects of our education system that relates to “the acquisition of technical skills, attitudes, understanding and

knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life". In other words, it prepares students in various occupational skills thus equipping them for effective participation in the field of work. To Asiegbu et al., (2021) educational development is very important in every society, reasons being that when people are given technical education and they become technologically inclined, society experience rapid development and innovations which opens doors and expands opportunities.

2. Statement of the Problem

It is no doubt that education helps people learn new knowledge as well as acquire appropriate value and skills particularly for their personal and societal development. Education plays a critical role in the development and progress of any society this is because of its position as the bed rock of any society as it drives societal cum economic development. Oranu (2010) notes that technical and science education programmes have been grossly neglected in Nigeria. Employers of labour and, very unfortunately, our law makers have not given technical education the needed attention it requires. Even though there are laws backing technical education in Nigeria, more still needs to be done. Most times you see teachers and technical unions lobbying law makers or going on long strike actions before attention is given to them. Scholars such as May (2007) contends that technical education continues to be underfunded, lacks adequate employees, lacks modern facilities, and lacks staff enthusiasm, robbing the country of the economic growth attributes that graduates of technical education may provide.

Another challenge facing most Nigerian technical institutions such as Polytechnics and technical colleges is in the area of curriculum for technical and science schools in Nigeria. Olunloyo (2002) noted that one of the issues confronting the design of appropriate curriculum for technical education in Polytechnics is the high rate of theoretical teachings and less practical's.

The slow rate of industrialization and technological development in Nigeria can thus be linked to the expanding gap between science and technology as a result of technical education's incapacity to effectively use scientific ideas to advance technology. As a result, it appears that technical education curricula in Nigeria should be overhauled in order to become more practical. It is against this backdrop that this study takes a critical look at the place of technical education in creating and imbuing innovative skills in citizens to withstand the throes of the pandemic.

Research Questions

- i. What are the possible challenges of technical education in Nigeria?
- ii. What prospect does technical education hold in educational development in post Covid 19 Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

- i. To examine the challenges affecting technical education in Nigeria.
- ii. To identify the prospects of technical education on educational development in post Covid 19 Nigeria.

Scope of the Study

This study focused on technical education, its challenges and prospects on educational development in Nigeria amidst the Covid 19 pandemic. The geographical area of this study is

Kenule Beeson Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic Bori, Rivers State. The study gathered the needed data from students and lecturers in the institution to achieve the purpose of the study.

3. Literature Review Education

To Fafunwa (1974, p.3), education can be seen as “ the aggregate of all the processes by which a child or young adult develops abilities, attitudes and other forms of behaviours which are of positive value to the society in which he lives”. Fafunwa went further to explain that education is a process of transmitting culture in terms of continuity and growth and for disseminating knowledge to ensure social control or guarantee rational direction of society or both (p.3). Hence, once we say a person is educated, we are implying that he is well cultured, enlightened, knowledgeable, and well-exposed and is socially, morally, intellectually and physically useful to the society. It is no gain saying therefore that social utility is a prerequisite for a person to fit into any society, hence the need for the acquisition of vocational skills and competence for self -relevance.

Technical Education

Technical education, to Uwaifo (2009), is the training of technically focused professionals who will be the initiators, facilitators, and implementers of a nation's technological progress. Uwaifo (2009) believes that educating students or citizens about the importance of becoming digitally literate will lead to self-sufficiency and long-term growth. He went on to say that, more than any other profession, technical education has a direct impact on the country's progress and development. This is because technical education imparts information and skills in areas such as electrical and electronics technology, metalworking technology, mechanical/automobile technology, construction technology, and woodworking technology, among others. Technical education is practical in nature, which distinguishes it in terms of content and methodology.

As previously stated, technical education facilitates the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge; it is thus a structured learning experience that begins with career exploration, supports basic academic and life skills, and enables high academic standards, leadership, industry-defined work preparation, and advanced and continuing education (CTE, 2009).

Technical education helps in the development of a creative mindset as well as having innovative skills all of which help in the attainment of our daily task. For Polytechnics, Section 8(80), of National Policy on Education (2004) outlines the following as their specific goals;

- i. To provide full-time or part-time course of instruction and training in Engineering, other technologies, applied science, business and management, leading to the production of trained manpower.
- ii. To provide for technical knowledge and skills necessary for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development of Nigeria.
- iii. Give training and impart the necessary skills for the production of technicians, technologist, and other skilled personnel who shall be enterprising and self-reliant.
- iv. Train people who can apply scientific knowledge to solve environmental problems for the convenience of man.
- v. Give exposure and professional studies in the technologies.

As is obvious, the above goals are very lofty ones which if pursued diligently would transform Nigeria into an industrial nation.

Covid 19

The World Health Organization (WHO) declared the Corona virus outbreak a public health emergency of worldwide significance on January 30, 2020 (Mahase, 2020). The novel Corona virus was given the code name 2019-nCoV and was formally dubbed severe acute respiratory syndrome corona virus 2 when it was first discovered (SARSCoV-2). Covid-19 is however the popular name. Like most global catastrophes, the history of Covid-19 is not very straight forward as there are two leading origins of the disease; some experts and world leaders believe that the virus was cultured in a remote Chinese laboratory for a sinister objective; while others strongly put forward the thesis that the virus is likely to have originated in the Hunan “Wet Market” in Wuhan, China, which many early confirmed cases had contact with (Nectar, 2020). At the outset, most of the patients with COVID-19 presented relatively serene cases. According to research and pertinent statistics from China's National Health Commission (2020), the proportion of severe cases among all COVID-19 patients in China ranged between 15% and 25%. The majority of patients reported a fever and a dry cough, with some additionally experiencing shortness of breath, exhaustion, and other unusual symptoms such as muscle pain, disorientation, headache, sore throat, diarrhea, and vomiting (Chen et al., 2020). Among patients who underwent chest computed tomography (CT), most showed bilateral pneumonia, with ground-glass opacity and bilateral patchy shadows being the most common patterns. Around one-third to one-fourth of the cases in Wuhan had major complications such as acute respiratory distress syndrome, arrhythmia, and shock, and was therefore hospitalized.

Technical Education in Nigeria: The Challenges

Technical education is designed to offer people the opportunity of improving themselves in their general proficiency, especially as regards their present or future endeavour. Over time, different academics have echoed the need for the nation to make effort and ensure technical education is taught at all levels in the nation's education system. In line with the above, Asogwa and Diogu (2007) revealed that there is an urgent need for Nigeria's attention to be redirected towards self-reliant and sustainable means of livelihood which technical education provides.

Oranu (2010) writing on the need for proper technical education to be adopted in the nation, observed that notwithstanding the idea behind the adoption of technical education in Nigeria's education system, it (technical education) still faces a lot of challenges like inadequate funding, staffing, etc. These challenges, he observed, can only be solved if and when the political will is adopted and a national commitment is made. Inadequate funding of technical and science projects has led to the turning out of ill equipped graduates into the labour market. This is because when there are no laboratories, classroom and workshop, students cannot effectively do their practical session which prepares them for the task ahead.

Awogbenle and Iwuamadi (2010) assert that in Nigeria, most students lack quality technical and science educational foundation, hence students lack the robust knowledge required for societal living. In line with the above, Okoye and Okwelle (2013) agree that students at the secondary school and technical college level do not have the necessary background to enable them pursue scientific and technical programmes at tertiary level thereby making them inefficient. Also, students lack the finance to pursue a career in the technical and science programmes and the government itself is not ready for student sponsorship in most cases. In the end, students opt for other programmes thereby making the labour market miss out potential valuable manpower with practical technical skills.

Another issue confronting technical education in Nigeria is the lack of balanced curriculum for technical and science schools. One of the challenges confronting the design of proper curriculum for technical education, according to Olunloyo (2002), is the high rate of theoretical teachings and low rate of practicals. The slow rate of industrialization and technological development in Nigeria can be linked to the expanding gap between science and technology as a result of technical education's incapacity to effectively use scientific ideas to advance technology. As a result, it implies that technical education curricula in Nigeria need be overhauled in order to become more practical. In line with the above, Ojimba (2012) established that Nigeria's present curricula have a number of issues. Our curriculum, he reveals, is based on foreign models, and there is a scarcity of fundamental texts in the area, with the majority of the available textbooks having a foreign origin and frequently illustrated with examples from outside the local environment. There is also a scarcity of highly qualified indigenous teaching and support professionals with appropriate technical experience to teach the contents of these publications.

Again, in Nigeria today we pay too much attention to university degree qualifications, regardless of whether or not the possessor has the essential knowledge and skill. Technical degrees, on the other hand, are highly valued in well developed societies. In fact, the countries, a person's worth is determined by his or her ability, inventiveness, and knowledge, not by the number of academic degrees he or she holds. To Nworlu- Elechi cited in Okoye and Arimonu (2016), graduates of technical education are frequently discriminated against in the public sector, and their employment prospects limited. As a result, secondary school graduates and their parents prefer university to technical education. When we do not appreciate our craft men and women (technical students in general), it passes a wrong signal to the upcoming generation.

In Nigeria today, because of the afore-mentioned limitations and other challenges, our technical experts and lecturers of technical institutions are leaving the shores of the nation in search of greener pasture in other climes leading to brain drain Bassi (2004) stated that over the years, around 45 percent of all Nigerian professionals, including technical educators, have departed the country. Nigeria lost around 10,000 middle and high-level managers to Western economies between 1997 and 2007. Each year, about 500 academics from Nigerian postsecondary institutions travel, primarily to Europe, America, and other African countries.

Technical education in Nigeria: the Prospects in a Post Covid Nigeria

Technical education, as stated, is a broad term that refers to aspects of the education process that include, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, as well as the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding, and knowledge relevant to occupations in various economic and social sectors (FRN, 2004). Generally, education is a veritable tool for national development which requires deliberate plan to suit the development needs of a nation. More so, it is always geared towards producing the right type of manpower in the right quality and quantity for the system.

Sequel to the above, the importance of technical education in post-Covid Nigeria cannot be overemphasized because technical education provides the knowledge, skills, and competencies required for survival and sustainable development in the post-Covid era. To Akpan (2002), technical education is the "gateway" through which practical skills can be successfully transferred for the country's survival. With technical education emphasized in our schools, it will help present students with brighter opportunity, knowledge and technical know –how to come up with new innovations which will help them survive this delicate era. The above is in line with the position of Kremer cited in Wilson and Asiegbu (2022) which states that investment in education

is a vital tool for development as a result of the different roles it plays in social cum economic development when the government invest more on technical education, it will lead to positive effects on both the economy, human capital and other sectors of the society.

Technical education revolves around science, technology, engineering and mathematics all of which Onyeche (2019) believes increases imagination, creativity, adaptability, flexibility, and the willingness to learn how to become independent. Thus, when technical education is made compulsory in schools, it will not just help students become innovative and creative, it will help reduce the unemployment rate in the country. According to a report by the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics cited in Onyeche (2010), the number of entrants ready for employment into the labour market drastically increased between 2010-2019 because of the establishment of more Universities in the country. The deduction here is that the national unemployment rate increased within the period as a result of the large number of unskilled graduates who left school within the period.

However, the inclusion of a technical curriculum into the traditional academic calendar would have drastically reduced the unemployment problem along with such social vices such as armed robbery, banditry, kidnapping amongst others. This is because only an idle and unemployed youth will think of causing societal unrest; an engaged mind would rather be technically oriented as well as innovative so as to solve societal problems. Technical education provides the opportunity for manpower development. This is because it gives room for the training of dedicated vocational and technical education teachers for the production of various levels of business and technical manpower to keep citizens above subsistence level of poverty.

Eneyoh et al. (2012) stated that technical education also provides a solid foundation for healthy multi-cultural transformation, which will reduce over dependence on foreign economies, resulting in human capital development, increase people's empowerment and hence national economic prosperity. Technical education has been identified as a tool for sustainable economy. In Nigeria, vocational and technical education was previously not seen as fundamental to national development but for school dropouts and never-do-well individuals. However, as stated by Okafor et al. (2018), no nation can progress technologically, industrially, or economically without a strong partner initiative in wealth development, poverty reduction, and job creation through technical education. The urgent need to equip the workforce for self-employment, as well as the importance of increasing the output of the informal sector, are two important goals of technical education (UNESCO, 2004). Governments in some countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, in particular, are redoubling their efforts to encourage technical and science education based on the belief that developing skills boosts production and keeps a country competitive in the global economy. Technical education thus serves as a form of orientation to the world of work, and its curriculum emphasizes the acquisition of such employable skills which are critical requirements for driving industrial and economic growth, as well as for developing the type of technical and entrepreneurial workforce that Nigerians require to create wealth and lift themselves out of poverty.

At a time like this when the corona virus has given us a big blow, the nation must invest heavily in technical education so as to survive the scourge. The National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) and teachers in this area should take up the campaign for more funds for technical education (Ojimba, 2013). When there is enough awareness on the need for technical education to be adopted or taught at every level of our educational system, it will give room for an imaginative mindset to thrive. The country must now begin to implement policies aimed at repositioning technical education for effective competition in the emerging global market after

the outbreak of Covid 19. The United Nation Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) have noted that revitalizing this sector is among the ways to improving economic opportunities for the youths hence ensuring sustainable development of the polity.

4. Theoretical framework

Human Capital Theory

This study adopted the human capital theory propounded by Becker in 1967. According to the theory, education, training, and development increase worker productivity by imparting usable knowledge and skills, hence improving workers' future wages by increasing their lifetime earnings. According to the human capital theory, a productive population is one that is educated or well trained, and that an individual's decision to invest in training is based on an analysis of the net present value of the costs vis-à-vis the benefits of such an investment (Becker, 1967). Individuals are considered to invest in training for a length of time before receiving a return on their investment. As a result, human capital is a form of production in which more investment means more output.

When applied to this study, we see students in technical colleges and especially technologists as major assets of the nation. As the nation struggles to survive the ripple effects of the Corona virus attack, one way she can effectively achieve this is through effective technical and scientific innovations and the only means to this is by improving our technical and science institutions. When tertiary institutions and others are equipped to take the teaching of technical education seriously, it will help us prepare our students for a better competitive world. When the government invests in the building of technical infrastructure and scientific institutions, providing practical and research laboratories it would help the nation produce technologists and technologies that would help us survive in trying times. As the world continues to search for efficacious vaccines against the virus, Nigeria can leverage on technical education and other scientific projects to manufacture vaccines, automobile, houses etc. Therefore, this paper supports the call for the inclusion of technical and science education in our curricular at every level of our educational system

Methodology

The study adopted the survey research design and the simple random sampling technique. Survey design helps in generating information with the aid of a questionnaire and it also helps a researcher to cover a large population during the study. The population of this study was drawn from the nine hundred and thirty (930) staff working in the polytechnic and the six hundred and thirty five (635) students across the different faculties and programmes that make up the four faculties in the Kenule Beeson Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, Rivers State. However, the sample size was drawn randomly from staff and students in five (5) departments, namely: Computer Science, Science Laboratory Technology, Civil Engineering, Accountancy, and Office Technology and Management. Both Primary and secondary data were collected to achieve the objectives of the study. The primary data were collected from questionnaire items on the subject of technical education while the secondary data were gotten from journals, textbook and newspapers.

The study administered 60 copies of questionnaires to each of the five selected departments totaling 300 questionnaires but retrieved and made use of only 258 copies of questionnaires to achieve the purpose of the study. A total of 10 questionnaire items were raised on the subject of the challenges and prospects of technical education in Nigeria amidst the Covid 19 era. The

respondents' responses were presented and analyzed in a frequency tables and with the use of simple percentage method.

Research setting

Kenule Beeson Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic Bori, Rivers State

Kenule Beeson Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic (formerly, Rivers State Polytechnic) is a State-Government owned tertiary institution located in Bori, Rivers State, Nigeria. The Polytechnic was established by the Rivers State Government in 1988. The then Military Governor, Colonel Anthony Ukpo inaugurated the provisional Council on May 13, 1988. The Edict establishing the Polytechnic was subsequently signed into law by Group Captain Ernest O. Adeleye, erstwhile Military Governor of Rivers State on March 25, 1989. He also performed the formal opening ceremony of the institution on May 19, 1990. The Rivers State Polytechnic (RIVPOLY), Bori, was officially renamed Kenule Beeson Saro-Wiwa Polytechnic, in honour of environmental right activist, Kenule "Ken" Beeson Saro Wiwa on the Wednesday, 29th July, 2015 after an executive bill by the state governor, Barr Nyesom Wike was passed by the Rivers State House of Assembly on Wednesday, 29th of July 2015.

Currently, the Polytechnic has staff strength of nine hundred and thirty (930) workers with five hundred and sixty (560) non-academic staff representing 60.3% and three hundred and seventy (370) academic staff representing 39.7% of the staff strength (Office of the Bursar, 2022). She currently has four faculties which are: School of Applied Science (Computer Science; Science Laboratory Technology; and Statistics), School of Engineering (Civil Engineering; Electrical/Electronic Engineering; Telecommunication; Electronics Power & Machine; Mechanical Engineering and Manufacturing Power plant), School of Environmental Technology (Estate management) and School of Management Science (Accountancy; Banking and Finance; Business Administration & Management; Marketing, Office Technology and Management; Insurance and Mass Communication) with a population of six hundred and thirty five (635) students across the different faculties and programmes.

Data Presentation and Discussion of Findings

Table 1: Bio-Data Analysis

S/N	Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Male	153	59.4
	Female	105	40.6
		258	100
2	Age		
	19-30 years	79	30.6
	31-40 years	93	36.1
	41 & above	86	33.3
		258	100
3	Marital status		
	Single	165	63.9
	Married	95	36.1
		258	100
4	Category		
	Staff	156	39.5
	Students	102	60.5

Field Work, 2022

Table 1 above depicts the bio data of sampled respondents used for the study. The study sampled one hundred and fifty three males representing 59.4% of the population while the remaining one hundred and five respondents (40.6%) are females. What this entails is that the study had more male respondents than the female. More so, while seventy nine (30.6%) of the respondents are between the ages of 19-30 years, ninety three (36.1%) are between 31-40 years and eighty six (33.3%) are between the ages of 41 years and above.

The study sampled one hundred and two (39.5%) students and one hundred and fifty six (60.5%) staff. The data proved that the study was able to capture a large population of staff who has a better understanding of technical education and how it can help proffer solutions to the challenges of the COVID-19 outbreak. Finally, the study recorded one hundred and sixty five (63.9%) as single while the remaining ninety three (36.1%) are married. This proves that the study sampled more of single respondents than married respondents.

Table 2: Questionnaire Distribution

Department/ Programmes	Number of Questionnaires Distributed.	Number of Questionnaires Retrieved without errors and were used	Percentage (%) Returned
Computer Science	60	39	13
Science Laboratory Technology	60	58	19.3
Civil Engineering	60	60	20
Accountancy	60	45	15
Office Technology and Management	60	56	18.7
Total	300	258	86

Field Work, 2022

From the table 2 above, it is clear that the study selected 5 departments/programmes from the different faculties in the institution. They are Computer Science, Science Laboratory Technology, Civil Engineering, Accountancy and Office Technology and Management. 60 questionnaires were administered to each of them totaling 300 copies of questionnaires administered for the purpose of the study. Out of the 300 copies of questionnaires administered, the study retrieved 39 copies from Computer science, 58 copies from Science Laboratory Technology, 60 copies from Civil Engineering; 45 copies from Accountancy and 56 from Office Technology and Management totaling 258 copies which was used for the study while forty-two (42) copies of questionnaires were not returned.

Research Question 1:

What are the possible challenges of technical education in Nigeria?

Table 3: Descriptive statistics on the possible challenges of technical education in Nigeria

S / N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	TOT AL	Mean	Remark
1	Inadequate budgetary	78	95	26	59	258	2.74	Accepted

	provisions for technical and science projects in Nigeria	(312)	(285)	(52)	(59)	(708)		
2	Most students lack quality technical and science educational foundation	89 (356)	69 (207)	23(4 6)	77 (77)	258 (686)	4.0	Accepted
3	Inappropriate curriculum for technical education colleges and institutions	96 (384)	67 (201)	39 (78)	56 (56)	258 (719)	2.78	Accepted
4	Lack of research grants, loans and student sponsorship does not affect technical education	29 (116)	62 (186)	98 (196)	69 (69)	258 (567)	2.19	Rejected
5	Brain drain of experts, technical teachers and lecturers of technical institutions who go out of Nigeria	98 (392)	66 (198)	25 (50)	69 (69)	258 (664)	2.57	Accepted

Source: Field work, 2022

Table 3 above had five (5) questionnaire items on the subject matter and was interpreted based on the frequency of the respondents’ responses with different degree of percentages on each as discussed below.

The result from table 3 above shows that technical and innovative education in Nigeria is faced with a lot of challenges. This is on account of the analysis, which proves that the respondents responses in questionnaire item number 1 accepted that inadequate budgetary provisions for technical and science projects in Nigeria affects the growth of technical education with 2.74 mean frequency which is above the criterion mean of 2.50. Also questionnaire items number 2, 3 and 5 where all accepted by the respondents with mean frequencies of 4.0, 2.78 and 2.57 showing that inappropriate curriculum for technical education colleges and institutions and adequate budgetary provisions for science projects affects technical education in Nigeria. This is in line with the view of Olunloyo (2002) who noted that one of the issues confronting the design of appropriate curriculum for technical education is the high rate of theoretical teachings and less of practicals. Furthermore, the respondent’s responses in questionnaire item number 4 with a 2.19 mean frequency was rejected as it is below the 2.50 criterion mean standard. This means that lack of research loans and sponsorship affects student’s zeal to be innovative and hinders them from conducting research.

Research Question 2:

What prospect does technical education hold in educational development in post Covid 19 Nigeria?

Table 4: Descriptive statistics on the prospects of technical education on educational development in post Covid 19 Nigeria?

S/N	Prospects of technical education on educational	SA	A	D	SD	TOTAL	Mean	Remark
6	Technical education and innovation has no prospects in Nigeria	30 (120)	50 (150)	92 (184)	86 (86)	258 (540)	2.09	Rejected
7	Enhances knowledge, skills and competencies	88 (352)	79 (237)	25 (50)	66 (66)	258 (705)	2.73	Accepted

	needed for sustainable development)					
8	Technical education has the capacity to improve general proficiency	91 (364)	89 (267)	21 (42)	57 (47)	258 (720)	2.79	Accepted
9	Technical education truncates students innovativeness and creativity	84 (336)	92 (184)	23 (46)	59 (59)	258 (625)	2.42	Rejected
10	Promotes technological innovations	96 (384)	67 (201)	39 (78)	56 (56)	258 (719)	2.78	Accepted

Source: *Field work, 2022*

Results from table 4 above shows that respondents responses’ rejected questionnaire items number 6 with mean 2.09 and item number 9 with mean frequency of 2.42 which is below the 2.5 criterion mean. This therefore means that to a large extent, technical education expands students and individual horizons and their ability to become innovative. Furthermore, respondents accepted items 7 with a mean frequency of 2.73, items 8 with a mean of 2.79 and items 10 with 2.78 mean frequencies. What this means is that technical education is needed in this Covid 19 era as it can help increase the competence, horizon and creativity level of students and individuals towards innovating solutions to the present pandemic. Akpan (2002) states that technical provides the necessary knowledge, skills and competencies for survival and sustainable development. What this means is that technical education serves as a gateway for to innovate and synchronize ideas that are needed in post Covid Nigeria.

5. Conclusion

Technical education is designed to offer people the opportunity of improving themselves in general proficiency, especially in relation to their present or future occupation. All successful nations, Britain, America, Germany, France and others, have over the years invested on technical and science education and that is why they are seen as developed. They have given technical education the attention it deserves as well as forging a resilient, patriotic national consciousness that gave identity to work with one mind towards the achievement of their present greatness. From the foregoing it is very clear that the position of technical education is a sign post to the development of any nation, Nigeria inclusive. Technical and science education with emphasis on engineering and other technologies can help us survive the corona virus pandemic; it can also give room to our young men and women to have an intelligent understanding of the world around them on the one hand, while leading to the production of craft men, technicians and other skilled personnel who will be enterprising and self-reliant (Epelle & Uriah, 2012, p.63).

Recommendations

Sequel to the above conclusion, the paper recommends as follows:

1. Nigerian Government and every stakeholder should give technical education the attention it requires. Our legislators, both at the national and state levels, should pass bills making it compulsory that every institution must teach some technical and science courses so as to help prepare students for the future. Our educational curricula should also be reviewed immediately. The curricula should make technical subjects compulsory. The curriculum taught in our technical and science institutions should also be reviewed to meet the demands of the contemporary labour market.

2. Technical and science education requires skilled and proficient teachers. The government should encourage the training of more qualified and experienced technical teachers. There is the need for regular training conferences and programmes for teachers of technology to upgrade their skills.
3. Government and other stakeholders should invest heavily in the provision of modern facilities for technical education. Thus, the government should give financial support to students and other technicians who need them so as to help them become creative and innovative in solving modern problems.
4. Government and other stakeholders should make technical and innovative professions attractive and lucrative so as to attract qualified personnel and as well avoid technical experts leaving the shores of our nation for Europe and North America in search of greener pasture.

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APPENDIX

Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Social Science,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education,
Rumolumeni, Port Harcourt.

Dear Respondent,

TECHNICAL EDUCATION IN THE COVID 19 ERA: THE CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

We are researchers from the Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Science, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt currently conducting research on the above subject matter.

You are by this letter, please requested to respond to the attached questionnaire based on your knowledge on the subject matter.

All information supplied would be used in confidence and used solely for the purpose of this research.

Thanks for your anticipated cooperation

Yours faithfully,

Alafuro Epelle, PhD

&

Asiegbu, Victor Iheanyichukwu

Department of Political Science,

Ignatius Ajuru University of Education,

Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt.

QUESTIONNAIRE

INSTRUCTION: Please tick good [√] in the box appropriately you consider to be most appropriate or that which represent your stand on each of the subject matter. Kindly read through all the questions before making your decision.

Section A: Biographic Data

1. **Sex:** Male [] Female []
2. **Age:** 19-30 [] 31-40 [] 41 &above []
3. **Marital status:** Single [] Married []
4. **Category :** Staff [] Student []

Section B: Substantial Issues

Please tick good (√) in the box that best suits your opinion in each of the items below with regards to technical education in the covid 19 era: the challenges and opportunities. The answer will be only type SA, A, D & SD (SA-Strongly Agree, A-Agree, D-Disagree, SD-Strongly Disagree).

S/N	Possible challenges of technical education in Nigeria	SA	A	D	SD
1	Inadequate budgetary provisions for technical and science projects in Nigeria				
2	Most students lack quality technical and science educational foundation				
3	Inappropriate curriculum for technical education colleges and institutions				
4	Lack of research grants, loans and student sponsorship does not affect technical education				
5	Brain drain of experts, technical teachers and lecturers of technical institutions out of Nigeria				
	Prospects of technical education on educational	SA	A	D	SD
6	Technical education and innovation has no prospects in Nigeria				
7	Enhances knowledge, skills and competencies needed for sustainable development				
8	Technical education has the capacity to improve general proficiency				
9	Technical education truncates students innovativeness and creativity				
10	Promotes technological innovations				